
D6.1
LL GUIDELINES, WITH LL TOOLBOX

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CEU: Central Europe.

ENoLL: European Network of Living Labs.

LC: Liquid chromatography.

LLIP: Living Lab Integrative Process

LL: Living Lab.

MED: Mediterranean.

RI: Research Infrastructures.

SA: Stakeholder analysis.

SH: Stakeholder.

SUEP: Stakeholder and User Engagement Plan

T: task.

WP: Work package.

PROJECT SUMMARY

AgroServ in a Nutshell

Ensuring a viable agroecological transition towards sustainable and resilient agri-food systems

Agricultural land depletion, the loss of biodiversity and the growing scarcity of natural resources are some of the complex challenges we face in this century. Whether due to the competition for land use or due to the tensions on agricultural modes of production, the necessity to adapt our current agricultural production methods to continue producing agricultural goods while concomitantly maintaining, preserving, and adapting the ecosystems, is a necessity.

AgroServ was thus born from the need for a collective action capable of enhancing the sustainability of food systems and food chains while safeguarding human, animal, and environmental health, and preserving natural resources and biodiversity, and mitigating climate change. The project was launched with the objective to better align (scientific) approaches and capabilities, and more effectively and efficiently use resources to ensure a viable agroecological transition towards sustainable and resilient agri-food systems.

By bringing together several types of expertise, disciplines, and technologies, and by integrating the competence and know-how of ecologists, agronomists, biologists, chemists, bioengineers, analysts, social scientists, and economists, AgroServ is designed to advance our knowledge of agronomic and husbandry practices. While there is a focus on the threats and risks of agroecosystems, it simultaneously supports the development of new agroecological practices by fostering transdisciplinarity and integrating a socio-economic dimension in the offer to researchers. AgroServ has 1) Research Infrastructures and 2) TNA across RIs at the core of its activities.

Summary of deliverable

This deliverable is the result of Task 6.1 (codesign of the Living Lab Model), which aims at establishing a learning and cooperation model and environment for running the Living Labs (LLs) with the purpose of building the suggestion stage for multi-stakeholder engagement, facilitating co-creation and co-learning activities, to enhance necessary cross-fertilizing interactions between researchers, businesses, producers, advisors, and end-users. The methodology will also represent a component of the training program developed in Task 5.3 (Joint training services for key end-users on operations from other WPs).

AgroServ Living Labs are the core of the collaboration between the academic community and the stakeholders acting as accelerators of the innovation process. They have been conceived as open and collaborative ways to translate research results into technological, organizational, institutional, and societal innovations, and, on the other hand, to facilitate the generation of new scientific questions which will be further researched with the support of AgroServ's services.

These guidelines aim to support the local teams of AgroServ in implementing and guiding the three Living Labs the project is aiming to set. The guidelines establish common terminology, goals, organization, and management practices with internal and external stakeholders of the

Living Lab, providing customized recommendations for the Research Infrastructures (RI) services they address and the connections with the others.

AgroServ Living Lab's ambition is to cover functionally, ecologically, geographically, and climatically multidimensional challenges of agroecological transition integrating economic, social, and political aspects. To achieve this, AgroServ establishes and runs three Living Labs and co-creation hubs in different geographic areas, supported by different installations of AgroServ's RIs. The three proposed Living Labs have been designed as co-creation open support ecosystems to address the challenges of innovation in the agroecology transition, with expected outcomes in the knowledge, business, and social domains.

In these guidelines, **Section 1** briefly describes the Living Labs to be implemented in the AgroServ project; **Section 2** is dedicated to an overview of the Living Lab concept, explaining the main characteristics and components that every Living Lab should have. **Section 3** focuses on the governance model adopted by the project's Living Labs, providing practical guidance for defining the main roles, for interactions among Living Labs, and between them and other project partners, as well as tools for monitoring the results achieved and activities carried out.

Finally, **Section 4** will be devoted to defining the various stages of the co-creation process, with a set of suggested tools for each indicated activity and some tips to ensure proper implementation of activities and a smooth co-creation experience. Moreover, suggestions for the Living Lab kick-off are also given.

This is a document that on the basis of the results also built on the constant interaction with Task 6.3 (Landscape & Trend analysis), as well as Task 2.2 (Developing AgroServ transdisciplinary approach supporting the Access Framework), Task 2.3 (Service pipelines clustering), Task 3.2 (Data deposition of experimental and integrative data), Task 3.3 (AgroServ data discovery and access to experimental and integrative data), Task 4.1 (Access quality management and TNA projects monitoring), Task 4.2 (Benefits of multi-RI access for multidisciplinary scientific challenges), and will be updated eventually in line with Task 6.5 (ENoLL Accreditation and long-term operation) which foresees ENoLL accreditation.

1. The AgroServ's Living Labs

The AgroServ project establishes the set-up of three Living Labs.

While sharing the same mission, the three Living Labs are heterogeneous since they represent different specificities:

- **LL1 - Multi-centered, trans-national Mediterranean LL (LL MED, Portugal-France-Italy):** LL Med will propose the solutions needed for the preservation of natural resources to cope with main threats in the Mediterranean region (climate change, drought, biodiversity loss, invasive species, decline in soil quality) while ensuring sustainability and resilience of agrifood systems. The territorial anchorage of agricultural (and cultural) practices is a capital parameter in the Mediterranean agri-food systems such as olive, citrus, and table and wine grape vineyards. Context-specific practical implementation of agroecological practices with low inputs, water needs focusing on closing nutrients and C cycling will be demonstrated. LL Med will provide resources and services for studying the possibilities of using organic waste or biochar as a solution to cope with nutrient imbalances and lability of organic C in soil; including agronomic quality and safety after landspreading; innovative solutions (smart, digital, eco-friendly, biobased, nature-based, etc.) and precision intervention at local and landscape levels for integrated, sustainable and effective management of emerging threats (invasive pest, water scarcity, climate change) and natural resources (soil, water, biodiversity) in Italy (CIHEAM), Portugal (UTAD), and France (INRAE). From a social point of view, the LL Med will contribute to sustainable territorial development by improving self-sufficiency and ensuring social, economic, and environmental sustainability.
- **LL2 - Central Europe LL (LL CEU, Czech Republic):** focusing on the sustainability of agrifood production systems, with an integrated food chain approach covering from primary production to food processing and preparation. This LL will apply an interdisciplinary approach to the sustainability of agrifood production, focusing on both farming and breeding practices and then food processing, covering biodiversity, climate change, environmental impact, plant protection, and breeding programs (including organic agriculture and integrated farming systems), food quality and safety, the nutritional and sensory quality of food in relation to primary production, processing technologies and preparation (cleaning, cooking procedures). LL CEU involves a comprehensive platform under the premises of CZU integrating experimental fields and greenhouses (e.g. for cereals, potatoes, medicinal and aromatic plants) and stables hosting different types of livestock (e.g. cows, pigs, poultry, rabbits) and a Food Processing Training Center (FoodTech Pavilion) with six main operation parts – processing of meat, milk, cereals, fruits, and vegetables, beer and oilseeds and medicinal plants. The lab is open to multiple actors: researchers, farmers, food operators (processors, producers, citizens, policymakers, and local authorities).
- **LL3 - Multi-centered North European LL (LL NORTH, Finland):** focusing on grass-based dairy and beef production in Nordic conditions including both mineral and organic soils (multi-centered Agro-LL in Finland, Natural Resources Institute Finland - LUKE, Kuopio Maaninka and Ruukki). LL North provides an interdisciplinary approach combining GHG emission studies to soil, water, and agronomical research, providing

data to LC -analysis. It is a comprehensive empirical research platform to examine and solve food production and land-use-induced environmental issues in the grass-based dairy and beef production chain from primary production to consumers. The holistic approach provided by LL North serves to prevent partial optimization of the production system and to identify the possible converse impacts of different measures which is a risk when multiple stakeholders are involved (retro-feed with tasks 7.1 “WPs support to ensure service provision sustainability beyond 2025”, and 7.2 “Governance and funding sustainability to ensure service provision sustainability beyond 2025”). The aim is to form a holistic view regarding options to mitigate the harmful impacts of agricultural practices on the atmosphere and water while securing food production.

Figure 1: Living Labs’ location and interactions. Created with OpenStreetMap

All data collected and produced by Living Labs will be managed according to WP3 “Consolidating integrated data management and analysis services” (T3.2 and T3.3), while fulfillment of ethics and quality requirements will be ensured according to WP4 “Access quality management & Ethics” (Task 4.1 and Task 4.3, D4.2).

2. What is a Living Lab?

The Living Lab approach is an innovative way to involve people from several sectors to work together to find solutions for common needs. The European Commission, especially in recent times, has been devoting relevant emphasis to it: “Innovation can no longer be the result of predefined and isolated activities but the outcome of a complex co-creation process involving knowledge flows and absorptive capacities from all actors involved across the entire economic and social environment” (European Commission, 2016).

The concept and the applications of Living Labs (LLs) are very dynamic and in constant change. In fact, LLs have been defined over time as a methodology, an organization, a system, an environment, and/or a systemic innovation approach. ENoLL (European Network of Living Labs), the most relevant international, non-profit, independent association of benchmarked Living Labs, defines LLs as “user-centered, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real-life communities and settings”¹.

Living Labs are real-life test and experimentation environments that foster co-creation and open innovation among the main actors of the **Quadruple Helix Model**², formed by representatives from all members of society: citizens, government, industry, and academia. The aim is joint value co-creation, rapid prototyping, or validation to scale up innovation and businesses.

Even if LLs can have different implementations, they all share a common set of key characteristics:

- **Co-creation:** The goal of Living Labs is to foster co-creation and collaborative contextual innovation through the involvement of diverse stakeholder groups.
- **Multi-method approach:** Living Labs utilize a variety of methods to aid in the design and development of innovations.
- **Multi-stakeholder participation:** Living Labs aim to support the co-creation of innovations by involving users and stakeholders and utilizing diverse methods. In essence, they offer a platform where individuals with a keen interest in a particular innovation can share their knowledge and skills to design and develop innovative solutions to real-life problems.
- **Real-life setting:** Living Labs engage diverse stakeholder groups in real-life settings, enabling solutions that are contextually relevant and tailored to specific communities or user groups.
- **Active user involvement:** Living Labs guarantee a high level of authenticity and engagement by promoting iterative interactions among stakeholders during the process of social learning and co-innovation.

¹ <https://enoll.org/about-us/>

² Carayannis and Campbell (2012)

Figure 2: Common characteristics of Living Labs (Source: ENoLL, 2015)

Living Labs employ a three-layer model, consisting of macro, meso, and micro levels, to facilitate the analysis of user research. This model simplifies the research landscape by describing the levels of analysis as follows:

Figure 3: Three-layer model. Figure taken from ENoLL. Source: Schuurman, D. (2015): Bridging the gap between Open and User Innovation? : exploring the value of Living Labs as a means to structure user contribution and manage distributed innovation (Doctoral dissertation, Ghent University).

- Macro level:** This refers to an organizational or system-level approach, which involves actors (such as public-private-people partnerships) and infrastructure utilizing open innovation

- **Meso level:** At the project level, Living Labs focus on innovative projects that utilize both open and user innovation. The Living Lab Integrative Process (LLIP) (figure 3), illustrates the innovation process at the project level.
- **Micro level:** Living Labs employ methods and tools that prioritize user innovation. The Living Lab Integrative Process outlines the different stages at the micro level and provides examples of tools that can be utilized during each stage.

The Living Lab Integrative process can be described as follows:

Figure 4: Living Lab Integrative Process (source: Mastelic, 2019; adapted by ENoLL)

The Living Lab Integrative Process combines and unifies the various components of the Living Lab Framework with the problem and solution phases of design thinking, creating a structured sequence of stages where diverse tools can be utilized to achieve the innovation process objectives. By incorporating the Quadruple Helix Model and design thinking practices, the LLIP provides a practical approach for implementing projects at the meso and micro levels of the Living Lab, utilizing a range of tools.

The LLIP methodology merges the design thinking approach (which uses tools such as “double diamond”, or “personas”) by introducing a problem space and a solution space while incorporating participatory co-design processes that involve the Quadruple Helix model in applied research.

As shown in the figure above, the Living Lab Integrative process is formed by:

- **Problem Phase:** the Living Lab approach involves researching the context to gain a thorough understanding of the socioeconomic and cultural setting, as well as the behaviors and practices of users. To integrate stakeholders, a People Public Private Partnership is utilized. Additionally, community-based social marketing is employed to identify potential barriers.
- **Solution Phase:** a common vision and shared goals serve as the foundation for the Living Lab approach, which involves co-designing solutions with users rather than for them. Real-life experimentation is then conducted to test and refine these solutions. Finally, measurement and performance evaluation sheets are needed to evaluate success and facilitate the scaling up of effective innovations.

- **Deployment Phase:** testing and demonstrating solutions in a real operational environment to prove their effectiveness. Once a solution has been validated, it can be expanded beyond its initial scope and adapted for use in different settings through a process of replication.

In light of the considerations expressed so far, it is clear that the Living Lab approach offers several benefits thanks to its ability to actively and continuously involve users during the development phase of new solutions and services.

ENoLL identifies 8 main benefits of using the Living Lab methodology:

1. Co-creation of innovation/solutions.
2. Mastering the value chain of the given project.
3. Identification of the key stakeholders.
4. Understanding the business of stakeholders.
5. Recognizing the value created for the stakeholders.
6. Development of management capabilities to create value for the stakeholders.
7. Providing strategic intelligence to guide stakeholders into value creation.
8. Knowledge transfer to improve value for stakeholders.

3. The Living Labs governance: roles and responsibilities

To ensure the proper functioning and efficiency of Living Labs, it is essential to have a well-defined governance system in place. This involves clearly defining the roles and responsibilities of team members, as well as developing a method for monitoring the activities carried out and planning those to be carried out. In this way, efficient management of Living Lab resources and activities can be ensured, enabling more effective and meaningful results for the target community.

3.1 The AgroServ Living Labs' Governance Model

A governance model allows for defining the executive leadership, who will be then responsible for the Living Lab management. The governance model has to include the stakeholders from the quadruple helix who can provide a direct contribution to the Living Lab activities. Consider that, in general, every Living Lab has its own governance model.

For the purpose of this project, we recommend that the Living Labs described in Section 1 establish a common governance model formed by two bodies, with the exception of the LL1 which, given its trans-national nature, will have a slightly different governance model:

- **The steering committee:** should be responsible for setting the strategic direction of the Living lab and ensuring that it is aligned with the needs and expectations of stakeholders. It should also oversee the Living Lab's operations, including the allocation of resources and the monitoring of progress toward goals. This body could be formed by at least 1 representative of each of the Living Lab stakeholders and the Living Lab manager (explained below), who meet at least every six months.
- **The management group:** should be responsible for the day-to-day management of the Living Lab, including planning and executing activities, managing resources, and ensuring that the Living Lab operates efficiently and effectively. For the scope of the project, the management group could be formed by:
 - **The Living Lab manager:** he/she has the responsibility for the activities and is strictly connected with the steering committee since he/she represents the link between the two bodies. Moreover, he/she is responsible on one hand for the communication and knowledge exchange with the Living Lab managers of the other two Living Labs, and on the other hand he interfaces with the leaders of other WPs.
 - **The Panel manager:** he/she is responsible for the stakeholder definition and engagement. He/she identifies the right users and stakeholders to be involved and together with the Living Lab manager defines their level of involvement.

LL1 governance model - For what concerns the LL1, given its transnational nature, the governance model should be slightly different. As explained in Section 1, this Living Lab is composed of three labs: MED A (Italy), MED B (France), and MED C (Portugal). Each lab will have the same bodies defined above (a steering committee and a management group). To these bodies, one common body at a “higher” level is added: **The transnational management group**. This body comprises the Living Lab managers of each of the three labs. The role of the transnational management group, a common body representing the three labs, will be that of exchanging information and fine-tuning the activities carried out by the labs, ensuring that activities and strategies are carried out in a consistent manner among them. In parallel, all three LL managers involved in the transnational management group will on one hand be in charge of communication and knowledge exchange with the managers of the other two Living Labs, on the other hand, interface with the leaders of other WPs.

Finally, a **Harmonization Board** will be created. This body, composed of the five Living Lab managers plus the WP leaders of WP2 (AgroServ integration and customisation of services), WP5 (Community building and users’ engagement), WP6 (Open Innovation Hub), and WP8 (Outreach, dissemination, exploitation of results), serves as the basis for sharing results, knowledge, and harmonization of activities, as well as fostering constant interaction between Living Labs and closely related WPs. The Harmonization Board defines the number and frequency of its meetings.

The figure below shows the overall governance model of Agroserv’s Living Labs.

Figure 5: Agroserv's Living Labs governance model

The governance model identified in these guidelines will be subject to improvements thanks to regular feedback from Living Labs. This is particularly relevant also in light of Task 6.5, which envisages following the ENOLL Capacity Building program toward their accreditation.

The interaction between the Living Lab governance and the Agroserv governance beyond the Harmonization Board will be guaranteed by the participation to the Harmonization Board, when deemed necessary, of the coordinator (leader of WP6, and part of the executive and management board).

3.2 Monitoring and quality assurance of the Living Labs

To ensure that Living Labs are able to carry out their activities effectively, it is important that they also monitor their activities and related outcomes on a regular basis. To support this, Living Labs can utilize two tools (see [Annex A](#) and [Annex B](#)):

- **LL Meeting Report:** a template that serves as a report to track all meetings and workshops held by the Living Lab. The template can be used to document key information from meetings and workshops such as attendance, agenda items, decisions made, lessons learned, and follow-up actions. This will enable the Living Lab to keep track of their meetings and workshop progress and ensure that activities are aligned with overall goals and objectives.
- **LL Reflection Memo:** a template (adapted from a template developed in AgriLink, an Horizon2020 funded project)³ that serves as a reflection memo to help monitor and evaluate the Living Lab over time. Each Living Lab will fill in this report on an annual basis. Thus, the reflection memo can be used to reflect on the Living Lab's performance over a longer period of time. It can be used to document successes and challenges, identify areas for improvement, and inform ongoing efforts to refine and improve the Living Lab's operations.

The monitoring and quality assurance of the Living Labs will be integrated with the project monitoring and quality assurance through the work of the Harmonization Board.

3.3 Operational checkpoints with WPs

As part of the overall governance and management of Living Labs, it is important to establish **regular checkpoints** to ensure that activities are progressing smoothly and in alignment with overall project goals and objectives. To support this, Living Labs can schedule periodic meetings with leaders from the other work packages involved in the project, as well as with the coordination of the project. The frequency of these meetings will depend on the specific needs of the project, but it is recommended that they take place at least on a quarterly basis. During these meetings, Living Lab managers can provide updates on their progress, discuss any challenges or issues that have arisen, and collaborate with other work package leaders to identify solutions and make any necessary adjustments to their plans. These regular checkpoints will help to ensure that Living Labs are able to stay on track and make progress towards their goals, while also promoting collaboration and alignment across the project as a whole.

During each meeting between Living Lab managers and WP leaders, it is recommended that the Living Lab managers produce minutes to ensure transparency and accountability. These minutes should capture key decisions and action items that are agreed upon during the meeting, as well as any updates on progress toward project milestones or other important goals. By creating these minutes, the Living Lab managers can provide a clear reference point for tracking

³ <https://www.agrilink2020.eu/>

progress over time, while also helping to ensure that all stakeholders are aware of the status of the Living Lab's advancements.

4. Living Lab Operationalization

Agroserv's Living Labs feature open innovation processes to co-create, validate, and test, in real-life contexts, RI services toward a resilient agricultural system and its nexus with the environment, health, and food security, also integrating those RIs services to support the development of sustainable agroecological systems. In order to carry out these activities, ENoLL suggests the use of the **co-creation flow chart** (figure 6). The chart presented is intended for Living Lab managers who are developing the co-creation process and its activities. It highlights various co-creation tools and methods that can be utilized during the different stages of the co-creation process. The chart is divided into four stages, each of them divided into two activities.

Figure 6: Co-creation flow chart. Source: adapted from ENoLL

For the co-creation activities described below, the majority of tools suggested pertain to the Co-creative toolkit accessed at <https://unalab.enoll.org/>. This toolkit, which has been developed and tested within the UNaLab H2020 project, provides a range of options to inspire and prepare co-creative activities. Facilitators can select a tool based on their intended purpose, such as identifying needs, generating ideas, developing strategies, experimenting with solutions, or gathering feedback from stakeholders.

The selection of a co-creative tool from the toolkit can take into account various factors such as the group size, the time available, and the preferred format of the tool. Additionally, the facilitator can assess the required level of facilitation as some tools may need more training and guidance than others. Thus, the toolkit is designed to cater to both novice and seasoned facilitators, as it provides valuable educational resources for individuals at all levels of expertise. Interactions and operativeness of LLs will be provided through the use of the e-platform (T6.2 Establishing the platform for SoLabs and Virtual learning-labs) and the demonstrators (T6.4 Establishing Living Labs and service demonstration).

4.1 Step 1 - From theory to practice: exploration and Inspiration

4.1.1 Living Lab Mapping

The initial activity involves the identification of the key challenges and themes to be addressed. Starting with relevant keywords, the specificities and objectives outlined for each Living Lab (see Section 1), and considering the desired characteristics of the Living Lab, it is important to focus on the **exploration** of elements that warrant further investigation.

To ensure a successful co-creation strategy, it is essential to define clear objectives and main goals that can help identify the relevant categories of stakeholders to involve throughout the entire process. In doing so, the following question could be considered:

- Which problem are we trying to solve?
- Where?
- What kind of activities are we going to perform?
- Who do we need?

The people involved in this phase are the Living Lab manager together with its team members. The suggested tools to use for this phase are:

- LivingLab Business Model Canva: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/19-qZmbmrcLeeerJ9NYdS7jn7VBM4z9cw/view?usp=sharing>
- Strategic Canvas: <https://unalab.enoll.org/strategic-canvas/>
- Mindmap: <https://unalab.enoll.org/mindmap/>
- SWOT diagram

4.1.2 Stakeholders mapping and engagement

This activity is dedicated to conducting a thorough context analysis that includes stakeholder mapping, with a focus on the most relevant ones. Additionally, it is crucial to assess the willingness of stakeholders in the value chain to adopt and use new services, solutions, processes, and innovations.

The process involves identifying and defining individuals or groups who may be impacted by the project, as well as their respective roles and relationships. Additionally, analyzing their interests, power, and level of influence on the project is a critical step.

Stakeholder Analysis (SA) is a commonly used decision-making tool that involves defining "stakeholders" (SH) and following specific guidelines for analysis. The SA identifies individuals or groups affected by a project or organization and systematically analyzes their roles, relationships, and interests. It also assesses factors such as interests, power, and influence, and documents and reports the findings.

Who are the stakeholders? Jones *et al.* (2017), identify stakeholders as agents who have a "stake" in an organization or project. These agents can be individuals or organizations who are interested and/or affected by the Living Lab, and at the same time, their input can have a direct impact on the LL results. Freeman (1984) provided a thorough and cohesive interpretation of the stakeholder concept. In particular, stakeholders are defined as those who possess particular

knowledge or direct/indirect connections to the project, idea, or initiative being studied. They have a vested interest and are motivated to influence the implementation of the specific project or initiative.

ENoLL identifies 3 types of stakeholders:

- **Internal and external stakeholders:**
 - Internal SH: Partners who play an active role within the Living Lab are considered to have an internal role. They will be considered and named as LL's Members
 - External SH: These individuals or groups have an interest in the achievements of the living lab but do not have an immediate association with it.

- **Primary and secondary stakeholders:**
 - Primary SH: They are directly impacted by the living lab (project) and hold the highest stake in its outcomes.
 - Secondary SH: These partners provide support to complete a living lab project, but their involvement is on a more general level. They fall into the category of partners who assist with financial, administrative, and legal processes.

- **Direct and indirect stakeholders:**
 - Direct SH: These individuals are directly engaged with the daily activities and projects of the living lab, such as the employees of the living lab team.
 - Indirect SH: This group of stakeholders is interested in the outcomes of the completed tasks and projects within the living lab, such as the customers of the living lab.

Although ENoLL defines the types of stakeholders as described above, for the AgroServ project we use the term "stakeholders" to refer to those individuals who are outside the AgroServ consortium, but who are brought in to play an active role within the Living Lab, becoming Living Lab members.

To **identify the stakeholders to engage**, an initial screening considering some questions could be useful to reason about their relevance according to the Living Lab characteristics and objectives. Some indicative questions could be:

- Do stakeholders have expertise in the topic of the project?
- How many stakeholders do we need to involve?
- What is expected from them?
- Can the stakeholders be considered relevant for supporting, testing, or implementing the Living Lab activities?
- How actively should the stakeholders be involved?
- Will the stakeholder be affected by the project results?
- Do the stakeholders want to benefit from the project activities also to reach their own goals?
- Are the stakeholders capable of implementing recommendations and outcomes?

- Can the stakeholders contribute to the improvement and success of the Living Lab activities?
- Do the stakeholders represent diverse perspectives?

The stakeholders can be identified among this indicative list of sectors:

- National and international agencies and authorities.
- National and European research agencies/authorities.
- Local or regional administrations.
- National or international organizations.
- NGOs.
- Consumers.
- Universities.
- Investors.
- Citizens.
- Media.
- National Standardization bodies.
- Relevant European associations.
- Relevant National associations.
- Research Centers.
- Others.

To ensure a comprehensive approach, the proposed methodology can facilitate the involvement of various entities through the "quadruple helix approach". These can include stakeholders along the product value chain, such as local clusters of farmers, small manufacturers, and distributors, public institutions, academia, research centers, as well as consumers. Thus, it is important to classify the identified stakeholders also according to the four dimensions of the Quadruple Helix Approach, namely Government, Citizens, Academia, and Industry. To achieve a balanced representation, each dimension should be adequately represented. Each Living Lab will be responsible for conducting the stakeholders' identification within their own contexts.

In carrying out the stakeholders' identification, it could be important to consider the following suggestions:

- Approach the identification of potential stakeholders with an open-minded attitude, taking into account various factors such as emerging markets and technologies, changing regulations and legislation, and other relevant factors.
- It is crucial to think strategically and politically when selecting stakeholders. It is important to keep in mind that different groups may have diverse interests and expectations, and a single group may have specific interests that differ from those of other groups.
- To ensure a balanced and representative selection of stakeholders, it is recommended to include representatives from various societal organizations, public bodies, the private sector, and scientific experts. This approach aligns with the 4 dimensions of the quadruple helix innovation system previously mentioned and can help ensure a diverse range of perspectives and expertise.

Moreover, it is important to keep in mind that **stakeholders' mapping is a dynamic process**, leading to continuous changes and adaptation of the selected stakeholders according to several factors (change in the relevance, finetuning of the activities, external obstacles, etc.).

To implement the stakeholders' identification, the **Panel Square canvas** (Koen Vervoort - Sync the Dots) shown below can be used since it helps to have in one glance who are the potential stakeholders to be involved on the basis of their relevance.

Figure 7: Panel Square canvas. Source: Koen Vervoort - Sync the Dots

How does this canvas work? Let's start by putting in the very center square who the users are. Then, fill in the four quadrants: each of them is dedicated to one of the four "helixes" of the quadruple helix approach. For each quadrant, the LL team members (Living Lab manager, Panel manager, and other staff that could be involved), based on the guidance provided above, discuss to identify potential stakeholders, placing them in the various levels according to their relevance: in the center levels, the most relevant ones will be placed, in the outer levels the less relevant ones.

With regard to the **engagement of the stakeholders and users** identified, it must occur in a well-coordinated manner throughout the whole project using the most adequate participatory methods for each exchange.

It is important to clarify that, by the term "users", we refer to those stakeholders to whom the co-designed solution is aimed, i.e., end users who will use the solution.

This activity is envisaged by Task 5.1 (Build a transdisciplinary community of users), which foresees a **Stakeholder and User Engagement Plan (SUEP, D5.1)** to be created to serve as a master plan for the coordination and detailed elaboration of specific stakeholder outreach activities and events. The SUEP is a living document and will be adapted to evolving needs of the project. This plan will allow tight coordination of all users and stakeholder activities and is closely interlinked to all the WPs that interact with users. In this Task, methodologies for surveys, workshops, and other events engaging users and stakeholders will be developed to serve WPs' needs and be documented to ensure transparency and repeatability.

4.2 Step 2 - Ideation and Design

4.2.1 The Co-creation Journey

First of all, it is essential to comprehend the local context and establish a robust stakeholder network, as highlighted in the previous stage. The co-creation process is significant as it enables Living Labs to define the problem, explore various options, and identify a range of ideas to be refined and developed further.

It is important to involve all relevant stakeholders who have an interest in the solution being developed. The ultimate goal is to generate innovative and original concepts also with the help of citizen support. A key component of this process is action planning, which allows for a deeper understanding of the needs and expectations of the selected community to avoid any disconnect between their ideas and the final outcome.

It is also important to ensure a clear and visual representation of the co-creation journey, for all the stakeholders, including those who will use the end result of the co-creation process (users). This visualization should be provided at each step of the process to ensure a common understanding and alignment on the approach.

For this activity, the following tools are suggested:

- Roadmapping: <https://unalab.enoll.org/roadmapping/>
- Idea Dashboard: <https://unalab.enoll.org/idea-dashboard/>
- PESTEL Analysis: i.e., Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal factors in the external environment.

4.2.2 Conceptualize and Design

The process of design conceptualization involves generating ideas to identify the best solution for a design problem. This activity, which is critical in the co-creation process, can have a significant impact on stakeholders' acceptance of the solution. Therefore, it is essential to involve users in this phase and enable them to contribute to idea generation and feasibility analysis in real-life settings.

The design conceptualization process involves collecting and analyzing data to identify the problem, brainstorming potential solutions, and creating visual representations of ideas. The co-creation process relies heavily on understanding the unique characteristics of the local context and involving citizens and stakeholders in the refinement of the final design. Therefore, it is crucial to gather all the necessary information and evaluate it accurately before proceeding to the next steps.

For this activity, the following tools are suggested:

- Lego Serious Play: <https://unalab.enoll.org/lego-serious-play/>
- Walt Disney Method: <https://unalab.enoll.org/walt-disney-method/>
- Co-co toolkit: <https://unalab.enoll.org/co-co-toolkit/>
- 6 thinking hats: <https://unalab.enoll.org/6-thinking-hats/>

4.3 Step 3 - Planning and Prototyping

4.3.1 Define your operational plan

To ensure the success of the co-creation process, it is important to establish a clear co-creation strategy and an operational plan that takes into account the needs of the targeted stakeholders and produces a relevant impact for them. Specific short and long-term deadlines should be set, and it is crucial to share the strategy with stakeholders to engage them in the subsequent prototyping and development phase. This engagement is essential for the success of the co-creation process. In this process, it could be important to assess potential risks and establish preventive measures for any issues that may arise during the prototyping phase, and draft a storyboard in order to have in one glance the steps for the implementation of the operational plan.

For this activity, the following tools are suggested:

- Ambition setting: <https://unalab.enoll.org/ambition-setting/>
- Vision development: <https://unalab.enoll.org/vision-development/>
- 5 Bold steps strategy: <https://unalab.enoll.org/5-bold-steps/>

4.3.2 Prototype and develop

To ensure the success of a proposed product or service, it's crucial to involve the targeted stakeholders in the testing and development phases, particularly when implementing technological and physical changes. User engagement is crucial for the success of the Living Lab solution, as it helps to determine whether the final product or service meets the needs and specifications of the target audience.

For this activity, the following tools are suggested:

- Design sprints: <https://designsprintkit.withgoogle.com/methodology/overview>
- Storyboard: <https://unalab.enoll.org/storyboard/>
- Open Innovation Hackathon: <https://unalab.enoll.org/open-innovation-hackathon/>
- Assumption Mapper: <https://unalab.enoll.org/assumption-mapper/>

4.4 Step 4 - Experimenting and Evaluating

4.4.1 Test the solution

The purpose of the testing phase is to assess whether the developed solution can effectively fulfill the users' requirements and expectations. It is not merely a means of collecting feedback from a group of possible users but involves a systematic set of observations conducted with users in multiple iterations.

For this activity, the following tools are suggested:

- Usability testing: <https://unalab.enoll.org/usability-testing/>
- Blink testing: <https://unalab.enoll.org/blink-testing/>
- Prototype testing map: <https://unalab.enoll.org/prototype-testing-map/>
- A/B testing: <https://unalab.enoll.org/a-b-testing/>

4.4.2 Assess your impact

This final activity is intended to evaluate the impact produced during the entire co-creation process within the target audience identified in Section 4.1.2. To assess this impact, a variety of indicators, including societal, economic, environmental, and technological factors, can be used. The evaluation process can be conducted using a combination of online and offline tools, and should consider both the short-term and long-term results and benefits that have been generated for the targeted stakeholders. It is important to involve the same groups of users who participated in the co-creation strategy from the outset in this evaluation process.

For this activity, the following tools are suggested:

- Dotmocracy: <https://unalab.enoll.org/dotmocracy/>
- I Like, I Wish, What If: <https://unalab.enoll.org/i-like-i-wish-what-if/>

4.5 Tips for Living Lab co-creation activities

It is important to appoint a dedicated note-taker during a Living Lab meeting to ensure that all the significant information is recorded. The note-taker should capture the highlights of the meeting, including any challenges encountered during the exercise, as well as interesting insights. This information can be used to enhance the co-creation process and identify any issues that need to be resolved. Additionally, the note-taker should obtain consent from the participants before taking any pictures during the workshop, or assign someone else to do so.

To ensure effective and unbiased facilitation, it could be beneficial to engage an external facilitator. An external facilitator can assist in keeping the discussion focused and provide all participants with an equal opportunity to share their ideas, ultimately promoting consensus-building among the group.

Note that in a Living Lab, there are no correct or incorrect answers. Participants should feel free to express their own perspectives based on their unique experiences and knowledge, without the worry of being evaluated or criticized. This is particularly significant when the Living Lab includes individuals with a diverse range of backgrounds and expertise.

It is also important to ensure that the language used is common and understood by everybody and allocate enough time for the participants to discuss among themselves in order to fully develop their views and understand the perspectives of each group involved in the Living Lab. This also implies that the information flow among the quadruple helix levels is adequate.

Try to implement a gender-balanced distribution among stakeholders, make sure to build trust with them, and keep constant communication to avoid the risk of losing them during the project.

4.6 Living Labs' kickoff suggestions

The kickoff of a Living Lab marks the start of its activities and sets the tone for the entire project. It is important to ensure that the kickoff is well-organized and that, once selected and engaged (see Section 4.2) all key stakeholders are present, including Living Lab team members, and other team members as needed.

To help ensure that the kickoff runs smoothly, we recommend that the following agenda items be included:

1. Introduction and welcome: the kickoff should begin with an introduction and welcome from the Living Lab managers. This is a good opportunity to provide an overview of the project and its goals, and to introduce the key stakeholders.
2. Review of project goals and objectives: next, the Living Lab manager should review the project goals and objectives. This is a good time to ensure that all stakeholders are aligned on the project's overall direction and purpose.
3. Overview of the Living Lab's activities and timeline: the Living Lab managers should provide an overview of the Living Lab's planned activities and timeline. This is a good time to discuss any potential roadblocks or challenges that may need to be addressed.
4. Discussion of roles and responsibilities: it is important to clarify the roles and responsibilities of each Living Lab member. This will help to ensure that everyone is aware of their duties and that there is no confusion or overlap.
5. Overview of the virtual working platform for Living Labs (developed in T6.2): this is a good time to discuss the virtual working platform for Living Labs and to ensure that all team members are familiar with how it works. This platform is intended as a tool for creating a virtual space of interaction among all the different interested stakeholders to share ideas and co-create solutions and services.
6. Q&A and wrap-up: the kickoff should end with a Q&A session to address any questions or concerns that team members may have. This is also a good time to ensure that everyone is clear on the next steps and timeline for the Living Lab's activities.

By following this agenda, Living Lab managers can ensure that the kickoff is productive and sets the foundation for successful collaboration throughout the project.

Furthermore, it should be noted that each Living Lab may make additional improvements to the suggested guidelines based on their specific needs and requirements.

ANNEX A: LL Meeting Report

LIVING LAB – MEETING REPORT

Insert here the name of your Living Lab and your location

<p>Title of the event/ overall topic (e.g. need analysis)</p>	
<p>Date</p>	
<p>Location of the event: (physical/non-physical)</p>	
<p>Participants (Stakeholders)</p>	
<p>Methods, tools, formates (e.g. open discussion/ mind mapping/ world café, miro board...)</p>	
<p>Main content (brief - minimum of 3 bullet points; please also name challenges or hurdles that were identified)</p>	
<p>Relevant outcomes (name at least 3 most important outcomes)</p>	

<p>Takeaways for Living Lab (lessons learned from the workshop)</p>	
<p>Outlook: Further ongoing activity from the meeting (yes/no – if yes please describe in short the upcoming activities)</p>	

ANNEX B: LL Reflection Memo

Annual reflection memo	Living Lab:
	Year (1st, 2nd...):
	Date:

The reflection memos are designed to help you monitor and evaluate the Living Labs over time. They enable you to reflect on what has happened so far and to help plan for the future. When completing the memo, please reflect on the Living Lab content as well as the process and also the context in which the Living Lab is situated. The questions below help consolidate previous learning and ensure it is used to inform current thinking about the Living Lab and your next steps. It will also be useful for identifying key points for the learning materials.

1. What has been happening in the Living Lab? (Please include comments on progress; the current state of the Living Lab; and if /how the Living Lab is developing/changing since the last memo.)
2. What has helped and hindered progress (explore why)?
3. What issues (if any) have emerged?
4. What have I/we learned in this quarter in relation to the Living Lab?
1. Summary of my/our learning so far (consolidation of key learning points to date including from previous quarterly memos and annual reports).
6. Any other insights & requests?
7. Any changes to your monitoring and evaluation plan?
8. What actions next and what rationale for action?

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